

INTEGRATE-LMedC

Mapping of Available Infrastructure Services for Large Medical Cohorts

Work Package 4 – Deliverable 4.1

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GLOSSARY

Organisations	
Abbreviation	Full Term
BBMRI-ERIC	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
Euro-BioImaging-ERIC	European Research Infrastructure for Imaging Technologies-European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EIRENE	Environmental Exposure Assessment Research Infrastructure
EBRAINS	European Brain Research Infrastructures
ELIXIR	European Life-Science Infrastructure for Biological Information
CNAG	Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico
Fraunhofer IBMT	Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering
Sciensano / HIRI	Sciensano/ Population Health Information Research Infrastructure
CTU Basel	Clinical Trial Unit Basel
BIN	Brain Imaging Network Core Facility
UMCG CBCH	University Medical Center Groningen, Cohort & Biobank Coordination Hub
FSJD	Fundació Sant Joan de Déu
UK Biobank	United Kingdom Biobank
Estonian Biobank	Estonian Genome Centre Biobank
SYNCHROS	Sustainable Network for Cohorts Harmonisation
ORCHESTRA	Connecting European Cohorts to Increase Common and Effective Response to SARS-CoV-2 Pandemic
IARC/WHO	International Agency for Research on Cancer / World Health Organization
Maelstrom Research	Maelstrom Research, McGill University
RDA	Research Data Alliance
IHCC	International Health Cohorts Consortium
Findata	Finnish Social & Health Data Permit Authority
NFDI4Health	National Research Data Infrastructure for Personal Health Data
France Cohortes	Inserm France Cohortes Platform
Health-RI	Health Research Infrastructure

Key Terminology	
Abbreviation	Full Term
AI Act	Artificial Intelligence Act
CDISC	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium
COMET	Core Outcome Measures in Effectiveness Trials
CRF	Case Report Form
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
EHDS	European Health Data Space
eIDAS	electronic Identification Authentication and Trust Services Regulation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDNG	Forschungsdatennutzungsgesetz (German Research Data Use Act)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IHCC C2C	Cohorts-to-Clinics model
LMedC	Large Medical Cohort
MixS	Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
NSF	National Science Foundation
OBiBa	Open-Source Infrastructure for Biobanking Applications
DataSHIELD	Data Aggregation through Anonymous Summary-statistics from Harmonised Individual-level Lifecourse Data
DataSHaPER	Data Schema and Harmonization Platform for Epidemiological Research
OMICS	High-throughput “-omics” disciplines
RD-Connect GPAP	Genome-Phenome Analysis Platform
SI	Specialisation Index
TwICS	Trials-within-Cohorts Study Design
XNAT	Extensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit
WP	Work Package

1. SUMMARY

Deliverable 4.1 sits in the first pillar (“Gap Analysis”) of the INTEGRATE-LMedC project. Its remit is to map the services, tools and capacities that European (and selected international) infrastructures already provide to large medical cohorts (LMedC) across the whole research-data life cycle from study design and governance to long-term data exploitation. The document creates the evidence based upon which later work packages will build an integrated, sustainable European infrastructure for cohort research.

ECRIN designed a survey and conducted follow-up interviews from 3 February to 17 April 2025. Twenty-five organisations including Research Infrastructures, national data hubs, biobanks, omics centres, European projects and international consortia completed the questionnaire; twenty-three among them participated in semi-structured follow-up interviews. Respondents reported on 14 core service categories revealing areas of strong capacity and where capacity is limited.

Beyond a simple inventory, Deliverable 4.1 explains why this mapping matters. This deliverable will be the basis, together with Milestone 4.1 (Task 4.2), describing the infrastructure services needed from the users’ perspective, for a gap analysis (T4.3) identifying the areas that require infrastructure support for LMedC in Europe. Knowing the types of services offered to large medical cohorts allows the consortium to, (i) run a meaningful gap analysis in Task 4.3, (ii) design a coordinated service model in later pillars, and (iii) guide EU and national investment so that scarce funds reinforce rather than duplicate existing strengths. It also highlights best practices and early lessons that can be fed directly into policy discussions around the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and future European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) roadmaps.

Finally, the document offers a snapshot of the current EU landscape: 21 of the 25 organisations provide data-centric services, 18 offer training, and 15 cover ELSI aspects, yet only 4 register cohort protocols and 5 support day-to-day study conduct, signposting immediate opportunities for capacity building. One of the striking features of this mapping exercise is the broad diversity of organisations/infrastructures providing services to cohorts and the lack of comprehensive coverage of cohorts’ needs by any of these infrastructures. This contrasts, for instance with the design and conduct of clinical trials, whereby the Clinical Trial Units (CTUs) all provide broadly the same spectrum of services, probably because clinical trials represent a highly regulated research area that follows highly standardised procedures.

Characterization of cohort services providers identifies five major service clusters:

- Data Services (e.g., ELIXIR, Maelstrom Research, France Cohortes, etc.)
- Regulatory and Ethical Support (e.g., NFDI4Health, SYNCHROS project, BIN, IARC/WHO, etc.)
- Methodology and Design (e.g., CTU Basel, FSJD, ECRIN, etc.)
- Biobanking and OMICS (e.g., CNAG, UK Biobank, BBMRI-ERIC, etc.)
- Operational support and Coordination (e.g., Findata, UMCG, Health RI, etc.)

Six cross-cutting challenges have been mentioned by partners in the interviews:

- Chronic, project-based funding that jeopardises long-term cohort maintenance.
- A fragmented fast-moving regulatory terrain (divergent GDPR interpretations, uneven EHDS readiness, differing national legislations).
- Technical interoperability gaps across domains and formats.
- Persistent privacy/ethical constraints that slow cross-border data sharing despite federated-analysis models.
- Shortages of data stewards and other specialist staff.
- Wide disparities in digital infrastructure, storage and secure-compute capacity.

To address these challenges, the recommendations of WP4 to policy makers, funders (and when applicable to service owners) are:

- Ensure sustainable, long-term funding for LMedC.
- Promote regulatory harmonisation and legal clarity for cohort research in the EU.
- Promote the use of data standards (e.g., CDISC, OMOP, DICOM, GA4GH) to improve interoperability.
- Improve cohort findability and access (e.g., through mandatory cohort registration).
- Build privacy-preserving infrastructures and tools (e.g., for anonymisation, synthetic data).
- Create EU-based GDPR-compliant cloud storage and archiving capacity for health research data.
- Invest in training and capacity building.
- Coordinate between existing Research Infrastructures and service providers.

The mapping exercise reveals a rich but fragmented landscape of infrastructure services supporting LMedC across Europe. Several service providers have expertise in Data Services, Regulatory and Ethical Support, Methodology and Design, Biobanking and OMICS and Operational Support and Coordination. Despite this fact, most service providers do not offer full-spectrum service coverage. This indicates the need to better coordinate the existing service offer to allow the infrastructure service providers to expand and scale up their current service provision to better address cohort user needs.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1. Context: Large Medical Cohorts (LMedC)

A medical cohort refers to a group of individuals sharing a specific condition, characteristic or exposure, who are followed over time to collect health-related data and/or biological materials. The data and biological materials collected from a medical cohort are stored as data banks or biobanks.

For the purpose of the project, INTEGRATE-LMedC, interventional clinical trials or databanks based solely on health registries without specific follow-up are not considered medical cohorts. A medical cohort is defined as "large" under the following criteria:

- Clinical observational cohorts with >1,000 participants selected for a health condition; or
- Rare disease cohorts comprising roughly over 0,5-1% of the total disease population in a given country; or
- Population cohorts with >10,000 participants.

Large medical cohorts (LMedC) are essential to public health and clinical research. They enable in-depth studies of both communicable and non-communicable diseases and allow research on various exposures, behaviors, and risk factors that influence health outcomes over time. These cohorts allow the collection of large-scale longitudinal data and biological samples from diverse populations, providing critical insights into risk factors, disease trajectories, and the effectiveness of health interventions and policies. LMedC offer qualitative longitudinal datasets that are not easily replicated through other research approaches. However, leveraging their full potential remains challenging due to limited data accessibility, fragmented methodologies, complex ethical and legal frameworks, and evolving data and regulatory ecosystems.

2.2. Objectives of Mapping of Tools and Services provided to LMedC

Task 4.1 serves as a foundational activity within Work Package 4 (WP4) of the INTEGRATE-LMedC project. Its main goal is to map infrastructure services and tools available at national, European, and international levels that support the design, planning, implementation, and reuse of LMedC.

This includes services offered by European Research Infrastructures (ERIC's, ESFRIs....), OMICs centres, public organisations and foundations, biobanks, EU-funded projects, international agencies / alliances / consortia, national data hubs and data infrastructures.

The results from Task 4.1 provide the empirical foundation for Task 4.3, which will conduct a gap analysis informed by the mapped services and the user needs gathered under Task 4.2. The combined findings will inform a strategic agenda for a sustainable European infrastructure supporting LMedC, identifying what needs to be developed or integrated to enable sustainable (re)use and harmonisation of large cohort data in Europe.

Deliverable 4.1 contributes to the project by:

- Establishing a baseline understanding of current capacities and services provided by the respondent organisations for LMedC.
- Identifying synergies between user needs (Task 4.2) and gaps (Task 4.3), to inform the concept design (WP18).
- Highlighting existing lessons learnt, best practices, and shared challenges to inform the design concept (WP18).
- Guiding infrastructure development including new tools, services, governance, and sustainability models.
- Supporting evidence-based policymaking at national and EU levels by identifying where investment or coordination are most needed.

3. METHODOLOGY

Due to their vast number, mapping all institutions providing services to large medical cohorts in Europe is not possible. Hence it was decided to include a representative range of institutions working with medical cohorts, e.g., European Research Infrastructures (ERICs, ESFRIs), OMICS centres, Public Organisations and Foundations, Biobanks, EC Projects, International agencies/alliances/consortia, National data hubs and data infrastructures. A targeted list of 28 organisations, primarily but not exclusively focused on Europe, was drawn up by the WP4 team and project partners. Each candidate received an email explaining the project and study aims, data protection conditions and expected contribution to the INTEGRATE-LMedC recommendations. Invitees who shared their consent received a personalised survey link and were offered 45-to-60-minute follow-up interviews to contextualise their answers.

3.1. Overview of Respondent Organisations

While the primary focus of the mapping was on European institutions, several international organisations were also consulted to provide a global perspective on service provision to LMedC. These include examples such as Maelstrom Research, IARC/WHO, the International Health Cohort Consortium (IHCC), and the Research Data Alliance (RDA). In addition, 2 of the respondent organisations Brain Imaging Network (BIN) and the CTU in Basel are national partners of Euro-BioImaging and ECRIN respectively and their inclusion in the mapping exercise was recommended by the RIs, to illustrate the specialised type of services they offer. Two EU projects (SYNCHROS and ORCHESTRA) were also included on the recommendation of the partners, and to get an EU project perspective into the mapping.

The 25 following organisations participated in this mapping exercise:

Organisation Type		Organisation Name	Geographical Scope
1.	European Research Infrastructures (ERICs, ESFRIs....)	BBMRI-ERIC	EU
2.		ECRIN	EU
3.		Euro-Biolmaging	EU
4.		EIRENE	EU
5.		EBRAINS	EU
6.		ELIXIR	EU
7.	OMICS centres	National Center for Genomic Analysis (CNAG)	National: Spain
8.	Public Organisations and Foundations	Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering (IBMT)	National: Germany
9.		Sciensano	National: Belgium
10.		Clinical Trial Unit, Basel	National: Switzerland
		BIN (Euro-Biolmaging node)	National: Portugal
11.		University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG)	National: The Netherlands
12.		Fundació Sant Joan de Déu (FSJD)	National: Spain
13.	Biobanks	UK Biobank	National: UK/ International
14.		Estonian Biobank	National: Estonia / International
15.	EC Projects	SYNCHROS	EU
16.		ORCHESTRA	EU
17.	International agencies/alliances/consortia	IARC/WHO	International
18.		Maelstrom Research , McGill University	International
19.		Research Data Alliance (RDA)	International
21.		International Health Cohort Consortium	International
22.	National data hubs and data infrastructures	Findata	National: Finland
23.		German National Research Data Infrastructure for Personal Health Data (NFDI4Health)	National: Germany
24.		France Cohortes	National: France
25.		Health-RI	National: The Netherlands

Table 1: Typology and Geographic Scope of Respondent Organisations

3.2. Survey Design

To map the tools, services and capacities that support large medical cohorts, ECRIN

developed a REDCap survey entitled “*Mapping Infrastructure Services and Tools for Large Medical Cohorts*” (Annex 2, Questionnaire). The survey was shared with WP4 partners for suggestions and was subsequently tested with two partners from the consortium to ensure it addressed all the important aspects of infrastructure services and tools for LMedC. User comprehension was also tested, along with the time needed to complete the survey. The final version was validated on 11 February 2025.

Closed questions provided a structured quantitative overview of infrastructure services and capacities. In contrast, open-ended items were designed to capture qualitative insights, which were further explored during the follow-up interviews. Major open questions focused on best practices, lessons learnt, and recommendations, and they were intentionally reserved for the online interviews. These questions were shared by ECRIN with respondents by email prior to the interview to allow them sufficient time to reflect and formulate informed responses.

The survey contains 13 questions that are organised in four blocks:

1. Services / Tools / Capacities
2. Access, Cost and Geographic Scope
3. Challenges, Best Practices and Lessons Learnt
4. Collaborations and Recommendations

3.3. Data Collection

Focal persons were identified in the 28 organisations mentioned in section 3.1. ECRIN sent an email outlining the study objectives, data protection conditions and the expected contribution to the INTEGRATE-LMedC recommendations. Respondents who provided consent received a personalised survey link and were invited to participate in a 45–60-minute follow-up interview to contextualise their responses. Data collection was closed on 17 April 2025.

Figure 1: Flow of organisational recruitment and participation in the Mapping Survey

2 out of the 25 participants who completed the online survey were unavailable for follow-up interviews. All 25 validated respondents were retained for quantitative analysis; interviews with 23 organisations enriched the qualitative findings. Survey responses from the two organisations that could not be interviewed were included in the quantitative analysis.

Timelines

- Draft survey questionnaire circulated to WP4 for feedback on 14 January 2025.
- Pilot tests conducted with FSJD and BBMRI-ERIC on 3 and 6 February 2025, respectively.
- The final survey was released on 11 February 2025.
- Data collection was undertaken from 3 February to 17 April 2025.
- Data Analysis and Report Writing: mid-April to mid-May.
- First draft report shared on: 16 June 2025, partner feedback collected till 27 June 2025.
- Revised pre-final draft circulated: 1 July 2025, feedback received until 3 July 2025.
- Final draft submitted to the INTEGRATE-LMedC coordination on 4 July 2025.

Response Rate

The response rate was 89.3 % (with 25 out of 28 organisations participating in the survey), and 82.1 % (23 out of 28) for those that completed the online survey and also participated in the interviews to provide more details. The non-response rate was 7.1% (2/28 organisations). Two to three reminders were sent out to all organisations, with the last email announcing when the data collection phase will be closed.

3.4. Data Analysis

The data collected through the REDCap survey and follow-up interviews were analysed using a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques to map the landscape of services, tools and infrastructures supporting LMedC.

Quantitative Analysis

Closed-ended survey responses (binary and multiple-choice) were analysed using descriptive statistics to assess the availability, distribution, and types of services offered. Responses were compiled using Microsoft Excel and the REDCap reporting interface. This allowed for:

- Frequency counts of service provision across 14 main services, along with sub-services for ELSI and data support.
- All 14 services were further clustered in five main areas: 1) Data Services, 2) Regulatory and Ethical Support (ELSI), 3) Methodology and Design, 4) Biobanking and OMICs, 5) Operational Support and Coordination.
- Cross-tabulations of service availability versus organisational type and geographic scope.
- Comparative metrics on access pathways and cost-recovery models.

Visual summaries were generated (Figures 2–11) in the form of pie charts and bar graphs, to illustrate patterns in service availability and gaps across the cohort research lifecycle.

Qualitative Analysis

Open-ended survey items and detailed follow-up interviews with 23 out of the 25 participating organisations were analysed to extract qualitative insights. A grounded thematic approach was used to identify key analytical themes including:

- Structural gaps and regulatory challenges.
- Tools and capacities in use and their effectiveness.
- Lessons learnt and best practices.
- Operational and policy-relevant recommendations for strengthening service provision.

Qualitative and quantitative findings were combined to validate results and reveal key patterns. Responses were coded and grouped to clarify the issues service providers face and their views on the way forward.

Integration of Findings

Interview feedback was particularly valuable for clarifying ambiguous survey responses and also to clarify any questions the respondents did not understand. Together, the quantitative and qualitative data sources provide a comprehensive view of the current service landscape

for LMedC in Europe and selected international contexts. This feedback is integrated in Section 6 and Annex 3.

Quantitative Analysis: Specialisation Index (SI)

To better characterise the service profiles of participating organisations, a Specialisation Index (SI) was developed to quantify the spread and focus of services offered across five functional clusters: Data Services, Regulatory and Ethical Support (ELSI), Methodology and Design, Biobanking and OMICS, and Operational Support and Coordination.

The SI measures how evenly an organisation's services are distributed across these clusters.

- A low SI value indicates a generalist provider offering balanced support across several areas.
- A high SI value reflects a specialist organisation with focused expertise in one or two domains.

This index provides a complementary lens to the qualitative and quantitative mapping by distinguishing between broad-spectrum infrastructures and those with a targeted service offer. For instance:

- Organisations like EIRENE and UMCG exhibit low SI values, indicating balanced engagement across multiple clusters.
- In contrast, CNAG and CTU Basel demonstrate higher SI values, reflecting their specialised focus on genomics and clinical research methodology, respectively.

SI values for all organisations are presented in Table 4. A full explanation of the SI calculation methodology, along with an illustrative example is available in Annex 2.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Services Provided to Large Medical Cohorts

The survey listed 14 types of services covering the lifecycle of large medical cohorts. The survey questions can be found in Annex 2.

4.1.1 Overview of Service Categories Offered

Figure 2 (below) displays how frequently each of the 14 core services is offered across the 25 responding organisations. While Data Services were at the top of the list (with 21 out of 25), Training and Capacity Building (18), and ELSI Support (15) were also widely available. Analysis of the survey results shows that fewer organisations offer operational support for Conduct (5) and Cohort Registration (4). Together, these figures help identify areas where future capacity-building could strengthen service provision and ensure a more balanced offering across the cohort lifecycle, e.g., Figure 2 data show a clear need to expand operational support for cohorts and improve cohort registration-related services.

Figure 2: Frequency of Core Service provision to Large Medical Cohorts

4.1.2. ELSI Services

The ELSI subset in Figure 3 shows strong coverage in areas like ethics guidance and data protection, while regulatory and ethical approval support are less frequently offered.

Figure 3: Subset of ELSI Support services provided by the Respondent Organisations

4.1.3. Data Services

Figure 4 below, illustrates the subset of Data Services, with most organisations providing support for Data Harmonisation and Standardisation (17), as well as Data Management and Secondary Use (15 each). Few offer support with early-stage tasks like Case Report Form (CRF) Development (7) or Cohort Data Sharing (9). The strong support for data management and analysis contrasts with limited availability of early-stage services, revealing an imbalance across the data lifecycle and pointing to areas for targeted capacity building.

Figure 4: Subset of Data Services Provided by the Respondent Organisations

4.1.4. Other Services

Five organisations reported additional services not captured by the predefined survey options, including:

- Findata: Grants permits for secondary use of health and social care register data, compiles and processes datasets, and provides a secure analysis environment and service desk.
- NFDI4Health: Supports FAIR health data through metadata tools, federated analysis, and a central study registration hub in Germany.
- EBRAINS: A distributed research infrastructure providing data, tools, and computing services via national nodes, covering a broad range of cohort-relevant functions.
- BIN: Offers PET and MRI population imaging not captured in the listed service categories.
- RDA: Provides data management guidance, including vocabularies and terminology standards.

4.2. Mapping the Service Provision Landscape: A Quantitative Analysis

This section presents a quantitative analysis of service provision by participating infrastructures, organised across five functional clusters that correspond to key phases in the lifecycle of large medical cohorts (LMedC). It includes both an overview of all reported services (Tables 2–4 in Section 4.2.1) and a detailed cluster-by-cluster breakdown of service capacities based on Specialisation Index analysis (Section 4.2.2).

4.2.1. Overview Tables: Reported Services and Specialisation Index

This subsection presents a quantitative synthesis of the survey data. The three tables below provide a structured overview of the services provided by the 25 participating organisations:

Tables 2–4 summarise the infrastructure service landscape based on survey responses.

- Table 2 shows the frequency of each specific service offered across all 25 respondents.
- Table 3 groups these services by five functional clusters to visualise broader areas of support.
- Table 4 presents the Specialisation Index (SI), which quantifies how narrowly or broadly an organisation provides services (see Annex 2 for the SI calculation method).

These tables serve as the basis for the in-depth functional analysis presented in subsection 4.2.2.

	BBMRI-ERIC	BIN	CNAG	CTU, Basel	EBRAINS	ECRIN	EIRENE	ELIXIR	Estonian Biobank	Euro Biobanking	Finchdata	France Cohortes	Fraunhofer IBMT	FSJD	Health-RI	IARC/WHO	ITCC	Maastricht Research	NEDi4th-Health	ORCHESTRA	RDA	Sciensano	SYNCHROS	UMCG	UK Biobank
Data Services																									
Data Management Plan		✓			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓							✓	✓	✓		✓	✓			
CRF Development		✓			✓	✓	✓	✓									✓	✓	✓						
Data Management Services		✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓					✓	✓	✓	✓					
Data Monitoring/Quality Control	✓	✓			✓	✓		✓	✓				✓				✓	✓	✓	✓					✓
Data Harmonization & Standard	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓					✓
Data Integration	✓				✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓										✓	✓	✓
Secondary Use of EHRs					✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓						✓	✓	✓
Cohort Data Secondary Use	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
Cohort Data Sharing	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓							✓							✓
Biostatistics and Data Analysis	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓									✓	✓	✓	
Other Data Services										✓							✓			✓					
ELSI Services																									
Ethics and Informed Consent	✓	✓			✓	✓		✓	✓			✓			✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓		
Legal and Regulatory Advice	✓	✓					✓	✓			✓			✓				✓					✓	✓	
Data Protection Advice	✓	✓					✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓		✓					✓		
Regulatory, Eth. App. & Amendmen	✓	✓			✓	✓					✓				✓								✓		
Infrastructure Services																									
Design		✓			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓							✓		
Methodology & Statistical Planning		✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓				✓						✓		
Protocol Review		✓			✓	✓	✓		✓			✓		✓						✓			✓	✓	
Cohort Protocol Registration					✓			✓			✓			✓						✓					
Planning (advice, research support)	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓						✓
Conduct					✓	✓	✓								✓										
Patient Recruitment		✓			✓		✓	✓				✓								✓					✓
Patient Engagement		✓			✓	✓	✓	✓			✓			✓						✓					
Biobanking & Sample Management	✓					✓	✓	✓			✓			✓	✓							✓	✓	✓	
OMICS Analysis	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓								✓									✓
Dissemination (e.g. Catalogue)	✓				✓		✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	
Training and Capacity Building	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
Other General Services	✓				✓					✓								✓		✓					

Table 2: Overview of all the services provided by respondent organisations to LMedC.

Cluster No.	Service Clusters	Services Available to LMedC - organised by clusters	Respondent Organisations Service Provision																										
			BBMRI-ERIC	BIN	C/IMG	CTLI_Basel	EBRA-INS	ECRIN	EIRENE	ELIXIR	Esoterica Biobank	Euro BioImaging	Finnfa	Fartec Cohortes	Faunhofer IBMT	FSJD	Health-RI	IRAC/WHO	IHCC	Maelstrom Research	NFDI4Health	ORC HESTRA	RDA	Scienceno	SYNCHROS	UMCG	UK Biobank	Service providers offering a given service	
Service Cluster 1	Data Services	Data Management Plan		1				1	1	1	1	1	1	1					1	1	1		1	1				11	
		CRF Development		1				1	1	1				1		1					1		1						8
		Data Management Services		1	1			1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						1	1	1	1					15
		Data Monitoring/Quality Control	1	1				1	1		1	1				1					1	1	1	1				1	12
		Data Harmonization & Standard	1					1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1			1	1	1	1		1		1	17
		Data Integration	1					1			1	1	1		1	1		1								1		1	10
		Secondary Use of EHRs						1		1	1	1		1	1		1	1			1					1		1	11
		Cohort Data Secondary Use	1	1				1		1	1	1		1	1		1				1	1	1		1	1		1	15
		Cohort Data Sharing	1					1	1	1	1	1		1								1						1	9
		Biostatistics and Data Analysis	1	1				1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1									1	1			12
	Other Data Services										1								1			1					3		
Cluster 2	Regulatory and Ethical Support	Ethics and Informed Consent	1	1				1	1		1	1		1			1	1		1			1	1	1			13	
		Legal and Regulatory Advice	1	1					1		1		1			1					1				1	1		9	
		Data Protection Advice	1	1					1		1	1		1			1	1	1		1				1			11	
		Regulatory, Eth. App. & Amendmen	1	1					1	1			1			1									1			7	
Cluster 3	Methodology & Design	Design		1				1	1	1		1	1		1	1		1	1						1			11	
		Methodology & Statistical Planning		1		1	1	1	1		1	1				1					1					1			10
		Protocol Review		1				1	1	1		1		1	1		1					1			1	1			11
		Cohort Protocol Registration						1			1		1									1							4
		Planning (advice, research support)		1		1			1	1		1	1		1	1	1		1	1	1		1				1		14
Clus. 4	Biobanking & OMICS	Biobanking & Sample Management	1					1		1				1			1	1						1	1	1		9	
		OMICS Analysis	1		1				1	1	1									1							1	7	
Cluster 5	Operational Support and Coordination	Conduct						1	1		1											1						5	
		Patient Recruitment		1				1		1		1			1							1				1		7	
		Patient Engagement		1				1	1	1		1				1						1						8	
		Dissemination (e.g. catalogue)	1					1	1		1	1	1			1	1	1	1	1				1		1		13	
		Training and Capacity Building	1	1				1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	18
	Total Services Offered by a Service Provider (in all 5 Clusters)	14	17	2	2	15	17	22	10	24	13	6	17	8	9	9	10	8	12	11	12	5	6	15	8	8			

Table 3: Services Provided to LMedC, organised by five Service Clusters.

No.	Type of Services Provided / Five Major Clusters of Service Providers	Service Providers																								
		RDA	ELIXR	Maelstrom Research	France Cohortes	Euro Biomed	NFDI4Health	SYNCHROS	GIN	IARC/WHO	CTU, Basel	FSJD	ECRIN	ORCHESTRA	CNAG	UK Biobank	IHCC	Fraunhofer IBMT	BBMRI-ERIC	Estonian Biobank	EIRENE	Findata	Health-RI	Sciensano	EBRAINS	UMCG
1	Data Services	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2			0.4	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.4		0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.3	0.3	
2	Regulatory and Ethical Services				0.3	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3			0.2				0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2		0.3	0.3		0.3
3	Methodology and Design			0.3	0.3	0.3		0.2	0.3	0.2	1.0	0.6	0.4	0.4			0.2	0.1		0.2	0.2				0.3	0.2
4	Biobanking and OMICS		0.4					0.2		0.2				0.8	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2						0.3
5	Operational Support & Coordination	0.3		0.3	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2			0.2	0.3			0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3

Table 4: Service Specialisation Index (SI) of Service Provision Across Five Clusters.

Table 4 illustrates specialisation in service provision of the 25 participating organisations supporting LMedC across the five service clusters: Data Services, Regulatory and Ethical Services (ELSI), Methodology and Design, Biobanking and OMICs, and Operational Support and Coordination. This approach highlights the distribution of activity within each provider’s service portfolio, without ranking or comparing providers against one another.

Data source: The values shown are based on self-reported responses from participating organisations in Section 2, Question 7 of the INTEGRATE-LMedC survey: “Which of the services does your organisation or project provide to large medical cohorts?”. Respondents indicated the services they offer, and these were subsequently grouped into five major service clusters for analysis and visualization.

Note: Annex 2 explains the methodology used to calculate the Specialisation Index (SI), along with an illustrative example. To improve readability, cells with a value of 0 (no activity provided by an organisation in that cluster) are shown as blank white cells. This helps highlight service gaps, distinguishing between low-intensity engagement and complete non-participation in a given cluster. In some cases, totals may not sum to exactly 1.0 as values are rounded to one decimal place for easy reading.

4.2.2. Cluster-Level Capacity Mapping Across the LMedC Lifecycle

This section presents a descriptive analysis of Table 4 shown above. The service provision landscape is diverse and fragmented: all 25 organisations provide at least one type of service, but not many offer a full-service model. Some organisations are generalist infrastructures offering broad, multi-cluster support, while others are highly specialised, delivering deep expertise in focused areas such as imaging, OMICS, or ELSI.

The services have been organised into five functional clusters:

1. Data Services
2. Regulatory and Ethical Support (ELSI)
3. Methodology and Design
4. Biobanking and OMICs
5. Operational Support and Coordination

Each subsection below provides a brief overview of service provision in the corresponding area, the number of organisations offering services, and the top four contributors (based on service intensity), followed by a list of other organisations active in that cluster.

a) Data Services

21 out of 25 organisations offer data-related services, making this the most widely covered cluster. These include FAIR data stewardship, metadata generation, federated access, secure processing environments, and data harmonisation tools.

Top 4 contributors:

- Research Data Alliance - RDA specializes in data services, particularly in developing recommendations and best practices for managing sensitive research data (e.g., [Metadata Standards Directory](#), [Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data](#) etc.).
- ELIXIR – Offers extensive compute resources, the [bio.tools](#) registry, and interoperable data-sharing standards across >20 countries.
- Maelstrom Research – Provides open-source tools ([madshapR](#), [Rmonize](#), [OBiBa suite](#)) and enhances data discoverability through its metadata-driven [Maelstrom Catalogue](#). Maelstrom Research also actively participates in international collaborations that foster and advance the use of epidemiological study data.
- France Cohortes – Delivers GDPR-compliant hosting, data collection/analysis tools, FAIR guidance, and cohort integration support.

Other contributors include: Findata, FSJD, UK Biobank, Euro-Biolmaging, NFDI4Health, SYNCHROS and ORCHESTRA projects, Sciensano, EBrains, Health-RI, BIN, BBMRI-

ERIC, CNAG, ECRIN, Estonian Biobank, Fraunhofer IBMT and EIRENE.

Service Gap: Only 4 organisations (16%) do not provide data services (CTU Basel, IARC/WHO, IHCC, UMCG), mostly due to their more specialized focus on clinical trials methodology, regulatory frameworks and international collaboration. It is important to highlight that CRF development is the least supported individual service in this cluster, reported by 8 organisations. This suggests that while infrastructures are strong on data handling and sharing, fewer support upstream activities like data collection instruments and design.

b) Regulatory and Ethical Support (ELSI)

15 out of 25 organisations provide ELSI services, though the level and focus of activity vary significantly. Table 4 shows that while some infrastructures integrate ELSI support within broader services, others specialise in regulatory guidance, data protection, and consent frameworks.

Top 4 contributors:

- NFDI4Health – Germany's national research data infrastructure for personal health data, currently developing an ELSI helpdesk. It supports metadata generation, federated data analysis, and cohort study registration via [the German Central Health Study Hub](#).
- SYNCHROS – A completed EU-funded project that produced international best practices and ELSI guidance to harmonise cohort infrastructures and improve legal interoperability.
- BIN – Brain Imaging Network Core Facility is a Euro-BioImaging Node provides advanced imaging technologies and data services for biomedical research, with a focus on phenotyping, image-based biomarkers, and longitudinal studies, patient recruitment, etc.
- BBMRI-ERIC – Provides dedicated [ELSI resources](#) including helpdesks, templates, and expert guidance across its biobank network.

Other contributors: IARC/WHO, France Cohortes, Health-RI, Sciensano, UMCG, ECRIN, Euro-BioImaging, IHCC, Fraunhofer IBMT, EIRENE and Estonian Biobank.

Service Gap: 10 organisations (40%) do not offer ELSI-related services, including major technical platforms and databases such as UK Biobank, CNAG, Findata, indicating a significant gap in ELSI support.

c) Methodology and Design

16 out of 25 organisations provide methodological support. These services include study design, feasibility assessment, statistical modelling, and support for harmonised clinical research protocols. This cluster is moderately well-covered, with a combination of cohort-level and infrastructure-level contributors.

Top 4 contributors:

- CTU Basel – Offers specialised services in clinical trial methodology including Trials-within-Cohorts (TwiCs) models.
- FSJD – Offers design and data management and harmonisation services. Coordinated the [SYNCHROS](#) project.
- ECRIN – Provides protocol design, feasibility assessment, and data and metadata management tools, such as the [clinical research Data Sharing Repository \(crDSR\)](#) and the [clinical research MetaData Repository \(crMDR\)](#). ECRIN also operates the [Regulatory & Ethical Database \(RED\)](#) with information on regulatory and ethics requirements across different EU countries.
- ORCHESTRA – [ORCHESTRA](#) is a completed EU-funded project. With a focus on COVID-19, it developed standardised cohort protocols and governance tools for pandemic preparedness.

Other contributors include: EBRAINS, Maelstrom Research, France Cohortes, Euro-BiImaging, BIN, IARC/WHO, SYNCHROS, IHCC, Estonian Biobank, EIRENE, Fraunhofer IBMT and UMCG.

Service Gap: 9 out of 25 organisations (36%) do not provide methodological services. This gap identification provides an opportunity for service providers like Sciensano, CNAG, Findata, and BBMRI-ERIC to expand their service offer by including study design and planning support in addition to biobanking, data integration, or policy coordination.

In this cluster, cohort protocol registration emerged as the least supported service, reported by only four organisations: ECRIN, Estonian Biobank, France Cohortes, and the now-concluded ORCHESTRA project.

d) Biobanking and OMICs

11 out of 25 organisations provide services related to biobanking and OMICS, making this the least supported cluster in our mapping exercise. These services include biosample storage, genomic profiling, and access frameworks for molecular data. Contributors to this cluster are typically either biobank-focused or OMICS-specialised infrastructures.

Top 4 contributors:

- CNAG – Specialised in high-throughput sequencing and multi-omics pipelines, a central hub for genome analysis in Europe.
- UK Biobank – A globally prominent resource offering biosamples, genotype data, and phenotype data from over 500,000 participants.
- IHCC – Supports integration of global cohorts, focusing on biosample-driven research and large-scale molecular data sharing.
- BBMRI-ERIC – Europe’s largest biobanking coordination infrastructure, providing access tools, quality standards, and interoperability frameworks.

Other notable contributors:

- ELIXIR – Offers services related to omics data management, bioinformatics, and federated discovery of molecular datasets.
- Fraunhofer IBMT – Combines tissue preservation, sample processing, and analytical technologies within a biomedical engineering context.

IARC/WHO, SYNCHROS, UMCG, Estonian Biobank and EIRENE are also contributing to this cluster.

Despite providing OMICS-related services, both BBMRI-ERIC and ELIXIR rank lower in the specialisation index for this cluster due to their broader cross-cluster service portfolios.

Service Gap: 14 out of 25 organisations (56%) do not offer biobanking or OMICS-related services. These include data-centric and policy-oriented infrastructures such as France Cohortes, ORCHESTRA, Findata, and EBRAINS. This does not necessarily indicate a significant gap in biosample integration and OMICS analyses within Europe as it has been a design choice to include only a limited number of OMICS infrastructures and biobanks in the mapping exercise since their service offer is rather standardised across different EU countries.

e) Operational Support and Coordination

20 out of 25 organisations provide operational support and coordination services. These include project management, service access assistance, user navigation, and infrastructure-level governance. This cluster is broadly covered, with both research infrastructures and cohort platforms offering varying degrees of support.

Top 4 contributors:

- Findata – Acts as a national health data coordinator in Finland, offering streamlined access, permit handling, and compliance guidance.
- Health-RI – Operates [the Dutch national ELSI Servicedesk](#) and supports access governance through its [Health Data Portal](#).

- Sciensano – Provides cross-infrastructure coordination in public health, supporting both administrative and data integration functions. Coordinated the now concluded [PHIRI](#) project. It supports data governance and metadata management. Driving the [HealthDCAT-AP](#) extension and metadata requirements within the HealthData@EU infrastructure in the EHDS ecosystem.
- EBRAINS – Offers structured coordination for users of its neuroscience platforms, including workflow integration, knowledge graphs and technical onboarding.

Other contributors include: UMCG, Maelstrom Research, ORCHESTRA project, RDA, Euro-BioImaging, NFDI4Health, BIN, IARC/WHO, ECRIN, IHCC, BBMRI-ERIC, Fraunhofer IBMT, RDA, IARC/WHO, EIRENE, and Estonian Biobank.

Service Gap: 5 out of 25 organisations (20%) do not provide operational coordination services. These include ELIXIR, CTU Basel, FSJD, CNAG, and UK Biobank. The absence of structured support in these infrastructures may reflect a narrower technical or scientific focus, or decentralised user access models. Within this cluster, services related to study conduct, patient recruitment, and patient engagement were among the least frequently reported. In contrast, activities such as training and dissemination appeared more commonly supported, highlighting a potential imbalance between communication-focused and implementation-focused services.

4.3. Focus Areas of Organisations

To better appreciate the diversity of services offered by the pool of organisations consulted, and to understand potential areas of coordination or gaps, this section explores the areas of focus and is divided into three aspects:

- the types of research data the respondents work with (prospective or retrospective).
- the disease areas they address.
- and the populations they target.

This section also confirms the heterogeneity in organisational focus, which suggests complementary strengths and potential for aligning services based on data types, disease areas, and population segments.

4.3.1. Prospective vs retrospective data use

Of the 25 participating organisations, 23 provided information on data use orientation. Among the 23 organisations that responded, 15 support both prospective and retrospective data uses, 5 focus exclusively on prospective development, and 3 on retrospective use. The RDA focuses on general data governance, recommendations and best practices and is therefore not specific to prospective or retrospective cohort support. The same applies to CNAG that focuses on genomics analysis.

This result indicates the need to strengthen service provision that leverages retrospective use of cohorts.

Figure 5: Organisational Focus on Prospective vs Retrospective Data Use

4.3.2. Focus on Specific Diseases

Whereas most respondents do not have disease-specific focus, 6 out of 25 organisations (24%) target specific disease areas. These include:

- Chronic diseases: cancer (IARC), diabetes (BIN), cardiovascular disorders (BIN).
- Infectious diseases: including sepsis and HIV (ORCHESTRA).
- Neurological disorders: Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, epilepsy, dementia, neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g. autism) (EBRAINS).
- Mental health and psychiatric disorders and personalised mental health treatments (SYNCHROS/FSJD, EBRAINS).
- Rare diseases: particularly those with genetic causes (EBRAINS).
- Paediatric disorders (SYNCHROS/FSJD).

Figure 6: Organisational Focus on Specific Diseases

4.3.3 Focus on Specific Populations

Of the 25 organisations included in this mapping, 20 organisations serve general populations, while 5 target defined populations. EBRAINS addresses the increasing prevalence of brain health conditions among older adults. BIN works with children, adolescents and aging populations. UK Biobank has a cohort, aged 40-70 years at baseline (around 15 years ago). ORCHESTRA worked with Health Care Workers (HCWs), elderly, HIV, hemato-onco, transplanted and Fraunhofer IBMT clarified that the German Environmental Specimen Bank that they work with for certain analysis focuses on young adults (20-29 years of age).

Figure 7: Organisational Focus on Specific Populations

4.4. Access Pathways and Cost Models

Transparent access frameworks and cost recovery models are critical for enabling broad reuse of cohort data and infrastructure, while also ensuring sustainability. This section explores how organisations offering services to LMedC manage user access, eligibility, and cost.

4.4.1. Overview Access and Eligibility

16 out of 25 respondent organisations have defined eligibility criteria or access procedures. Examples include:

- In many cases, access committees are employed to assess project proposals based on scientific merit. Applications for some service provision can be accepted even without scientific review if the research serves the public interest and is conducted by a Bonafide researcher. Some organisations base eligibility on geographic scope, research focus and potential impact. For some service providers, applications may first be reviewed by ethics committees prior to further processing.

- Applicants must submit a short protocol via the organisation's webpage, which is reviewed by an RI board along with an ethics and feasibility check. Criteria may include the principal investigator's scientific credentials and laboratory capacities.
- At EBiSC, institutions worldwide may access cell lines (subject to cost and national restrictions). Associated genetic data are stored at EGA and managed by a data access committee. Public data from the human pluripotent stem cell registry are enhanced with APIs for machine readability of the data.
- Support is limited to cohorts coordinated by their own organisation for University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG) and Fundació Sant Joan de Déu (FSJD). The same applies in practice for the statistical services of the Clinical Trial Unit in Basel, where most of the services are expected to be delivered at institutional (or regional/national level).

Eligibility criteria or access procedures in place for providing services to LMedC?	
Name of the Organisation	Yes/No
BBMRI-ERIC	No
Brain Imaging Network Core Facility (BIN)- EuBI node	Yes
Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico (CNAG)	Yes
Clinical Trial Unit, Basel, ECRIN CTU network	No
EBRAINS	Other
ECRIN	Yes
EIRENE	Yes
ELIXIR	Yes, Other
Estonian Biobank	Yes
Euro-Biolmaging	Yes
Findata	Yes, Other
France Cohortes	Yes
Fraunhofer Society for Applied Research, Institute for Biomedical Engineering (IBMT)	Yes
Fundació Sant Joan de Déu (FSJD)	No
Health-RI	No
IARC/WHO	Yes
International Health Cohorts Consortium (IHCC)	Yes
Maelstrom Research	No
NFDI4Health	Yes, Other
ORCHESTRA	Yes
RDA	No
Sciensano	No
SYNCHROS	Yes
UK Biobank	Yes
University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG), Cohort and Biobank Coordination Hub	Other

Table 5: Access and Eligibility Procedures Across Organisations.

4.4.2. Access pathways: virtual, consulting, operational

Organisations support different access models: virtual (e.g., online catalogues and federated access), consulting-based (through expert review and coordination), and operational (direct support or infrastructure use). Among the respondent organisations, access is provided using different models, sometimes all four or in different combinations.

Figure 8: Types of Access Pathways Supported by Respondent Organisations

4 respondents selected “Other Access Models”, often because they were unsure how to classify their access pathway. Their answers include:

NFDI4Health provides open metadata access (if GDPR-compliant) via a portal designed to make data findable. Tools are openly accessible without restrictions.

Findata offers regulated access to health data in Finland. Researchers must declare GDPR compliance, specify data needs, and state the research purpose. While there is a fee for services, no scientific or ethical board review is required.

EBRAINS employs an open and collaborative access model to provide its services, ensuring that researchers can effectively utilize its resources. Here are the key aspects of this model:

- 1. Open Access** - EBRAINS promotes open access to its tools, data, and computing facilities. Most of the services and tools are available without registration via the EBRAINS portal.
- 2. Registration and User Accounts** - Researchers from across Europe and beyond can register to use additional EBRAINS' services such as Collaboratory and Jupyter Labs. This involves agreeing to the terms of use and privacy policy, ensuring compliance with ethical and legal standards.
- 3. Consulting and Support** - EBRAINS offers technical and scientific consulting services to help researchers integrate their tools into their workflows, optimize data management, including data and metadata collection and metadata standardization. This support ensures that users can fully benefit from the available resources.

ELIXIR provides controlled virtual access services, such as reusing sensitive datasets in the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA).

4.4.3. Cost recovery approaches

Many (17 out of 25) of the respondent organisations offer their services within collaborative research projects (e.g., EC grants) and in case that funding from projects is not available, fees are charged for the service provision (17 out of 25). Some organisations (10) receive also sustainable core funding for their service provision (e.g., Health-RI, Estonian Biobank, UK Biobank).

Figure 9: Different cost-recovery models for provision of services.

Interestingly, some “Other” cost-recovery models were mentioned by the respondents:

- EBRAINS, ELIXIR, ECRIN, BBMRI-ERIC, EIRENE are co-funded by Member State contributions. This is the case also for other ESFRIs.
- Sciensano noted in their survey response that they are in the process of setting up PHIRI (the Population Health Information Research Infrastructure) as legal entity and the access procedure and cost-recovery model have still to be agreed.
- Among other sources of funding, UK Biobank also receives funding through philanthropy.
- NFDI4Health services are currently free of charge, since they are funded as part of a national project in Germany. A business model will be developed within the project to cover costs in the future to make the services sustainable.

4.5. Geographic Reach of Services

In terms of geographic coverage, a relatively similar number of respondents provide services at the national (17 out of 25) and European (16 out of 25) levels, with a lower number providing services at the global (12 out of 25) level. Despite the fact that this mapping exercise is not exhaustive, it demonstrates that relevant service provision exists and could be leveraged or expanded to better correspond to user needs.

Figure 10: Pie Chart of Geographic Coverage of Service Provision

The detailed responses of the participating organisations are provided in Table 6 below:

Name of Org.	National	Regional	European	Global	Other
BBMRI-ERIC	✓	✓	✓	✓	
BIN	✓		✓		
CNAG	✓	✓	✓	✓	
CTU, Basel		✓			
EBRAINS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ECRIN			✓		
EIRENE	✓	✓			
ELIXIR			✓	✓	
Estonian Biobank	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Euro Biolmaging	✓	✓	✓		
Findata	✓		✓	✓	
France Cohortes	✓				
Fraunhofer IBMT	✓		✓	✓	
FSJD	✓	✓	✓		
Health-RI	✓				
IARC/WHO				✓	
IHCC				✓	
Maelstrom Resear	✓	✓	✓	✓	
NFDI4Health	✓		✓		
ORCHESTRA	✓	✓	✓		
RDA	✓		✓	✓	
Sciensano			✓		
SYNCHROS		✓			
UK Biobank				✓	
UMCG	✓	✓			✓
Total	17	12	16	12	2

Table 6: Details of Geographic Coverage of Respondents.

Two organisations chose “Other” to share other models of service provision that fall outside the categories provided in the questionnaire or to enable “free text” explanation for their selection.

EBRAINS: offers virtual access to its resources, allowing researchers to use its tools and services remotely from anywhere in the world. This includes access to advanced digital tools, data repositories, and high-performance computing resources through cloud-based platforms.

UMCG: This reach varies by service. Most are oriented towards local UMCG cohorts, although some policy development activities are conducted at national level.

5. DISCUSSION

This section synthesises the main insights emerging from the mapping exercise. While the results show a vibrant and diverse infrastructure landscape supporting LMedC across Europe, interviews and survey responses also revealed key structural, regulatory, and technical challenges. Based on these insights, we present examples of best practices already being implemented, and conclude with strategic recommendations aimed at policymakers, funders, and service providers.

5.1. Challenges Identified in Service Provision

The survey and the follow-up interviews conducted as part of WP4, mapping exercise, surfaced several recurring and systemic challenges that hinder the optimal use, expansion, and sustainability of LMedC across Europe. These challenges fall into six interrelated categories: 1) Funding Limitations, 2) Changing Regulatory Ecosystem, 3) Evolving Data Ecosystem, 4) Privacy, Security and Ethical Concerns, 5) Insufficient Personnel and 6) Technology Gaps. The respondents could also report in free text “Other challenges” that they identified.

Figure 11 highlights the challenges that were seen as most important by the service providers.

Figure 11: Challenges in Service Provision by the Respondent Organisations

5.1.1. Funding Limitations

Funding limitations are mentioned by 19 out of the 25 survey respondents. Funding challenges exist at the national, European, and international levels, posing a major barrier to the long-term sustainability of cohort and longitudinal studies, creating discontinuities in service provision and infrastructure development. These studies require stable, predictable financing over extended periods to maintain infrastructure, retain expertise, and enable consistent data collection. Without sustained funding, essential services such as biobanking, long-term archiving, or metadata curation remain vulnerable to collapse.

Where core funding and long-term institutional support are available, they contribute positively to sustained collaboration and to the overall resilience of the research infrastructure ecosystem. However, many funding streams remain project-based, often limited to short cycles. Setting up large-scale cohort projects typically involves long preparatory phases, often taking six months or more, and budgets are frequently uncertain from year to year, making strategic planning difficult. The ability to forecast and secure multi-year budgets is critical, yet current funding mechanisms often fail to provide such predictability. Stronger alignment between funding instruments and the long-term nature of cohorts is urgently needed.

5.1.2. Changing Regulatory Ecosystem

Challenges related to the changing regulatory ecosystem are mentioned by 18 out of the 25 survey respondents. The European regulatory landscape for health and research data remains highly fragmented, with Member States progressing at different speeds in developing or implementing national legislation that governs the secondary use of health data for research. While some countries have well-defined legal frameworks, others are still in the process of adapting or drafting such legislation.

In Germany, the [*Gesundheitsdatennutzungsgesetz \(GDNG\) or Health Data Use Act \(2024\)*](#) represents a key national initiative aimed at improving access to health data for research purposes. It establishes a centralised data access point to support scientific use, addressing longstanding fragmentation in the national data governance framework. Finland introduced a pioneering model through the [*Act on the Secondary Use of Health and Social Data \(2019\)*](#), which led to the establishment of Findata, a centralised authority that issues data permits across public and private sector health and social welfare registers. Findata also provides a Secure Processing Environment for data use, representing a best-practice example within the EU. In the Netherlands, the control and governance of bodily materials is regulated by the [*Dutch Civil Code, Book 7, Article 467 \(WGBO\)*](#), which mandates explicit donor consent for the use of biological samples beyond direct medical care and guarantees the right to withdraw that consent at any time.

To facilitate public health preparedness and transnational cohort studies, a derogation

mechanism should be considered under GDPR for research conducted in the public interest including in areas such as vaccination, prevention, and infectious disease surveillance. Without such legal flexibility, a future pandemic could again face severe delays: ethics approvals and data-sharing agreements across multiple sites can take months.

[The European Health Data Space \(EHDS\)](#) represents another transformative regulation that “promises” to harmonise data access and reuse but with the details of its implementation still forthcoming, its capacity to resolve legal divergence remains uncertain. There is concern about how the EHDS will impact the already complex cohort ecosystem. Cohort and clinical trial data access is expected to be managed via the national Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs), which may lack experience with research-specific data governance. In addition, the way the EHDS ecosystem is currently foreseen has been shaped with the example of Electronic Health Record (EHR) reuse and it is unclear whether it will be a good fit for clinical research data (cohort, trial). In addition, Health DCAT-AP, the expected metadata schema to be used for catalogues within the EHDS ecosystem, is still a moving target.

In the context of clinical trials, the [Clinical Trials Information System \(CTIS\)](#), launched under the [EU Clinical Trials Regulation \(Regulation EU No. 536/2014\)](#), became mandatory for all new clinical trial applications from 31 January 2023, with full migration of ongoing trials required by 31 January 2025. However, implementation has faced several challenges, including metadata model misalignment between CTIS and existing trial registries or sponsor systems. This affected initiatives such as NFDI4Health, which encountered difficulties aligning clinical study metadata with CTIS requirements.

The adoption of the [EU Artificial Intelligence Act \(AI Act\)](#) on 13 March 2024 and expected to enter into force in mid-2025, introduces a risk-based framework for AI systems, including those used in health and research. While intended to safeguard rights and ensure responsible AI deployment, questions remain about how the Act will impact cohort-based AI applications, particularly in defining data-sharing thresholds and anonymisation protocols. Anonymisation standards continue to vary across Member States, complicating the implementation of AI in cross-border research settings.

5.1.3. Evolving Data Ecosystem

Challenges related to the evolving data ecosystem are mentioned by 15 out of the 25 survey respondents. For big datasets, including omics and imaging, there is an urgent need for cost-effective data storage and long-term archiving infrastructure reported by different survey participants in different countries across the EU. In addition, LMedC do not often apply data standards such as CDISC or OMOP. For imaging, sometimes the XNAT platform and the DICOM standard are used. The lack of adoption of data standards in LMedC and the lack of interoperability among them further hinders data reuse. Moreover, extracting clinical data directly from EHRs remains complex. Harmonisation is also required in data

access and reuse processes across the EU (e.g., more standardisation in data transfer and data reuse agreements, adequate consent forms for cohort participants). In parallel, organisations across Europe report gaps in the software landscape, particularly in relation to the deployment of AI applications, which require high-quality, interoperable data as input.

5.1.4. Privacy, Security and Ethical Concerns

Challenges related to privacy, security, and ethics are mentioned by 14 out of the 25 survey respondents. One key approach to addressing these concerns is the use of distributed analysis/computing models, which allow data to remain within its original institution (and jurisdiction). In this setup, analysis code is sent to the data-holding site, executed locally, and only aggregate, non-identifiable results are returned to researchers for further integration. Distributed analysis/computing is increasingly recognised as an effective method for mitigating risks related to data privacy, ethical compliance, and information security. Trusted Research Environments (TREs) or Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) are expected to play an important role in enabling secure access to health-related data in the near future. For example, the UK Biobank is introducing an “Airlock” model, a secure research analysis platform that prohibits data downloads entirely, thus preventing unauthorised transfers.

A commonly accepted definition of “anonymisation” and validation methodologies for synthetic datasets would also facilitate the wider use of LMedC. For example, genomic data presents long-term privacy challenges as advances in interpretation may enable future re-identification or risk scoring. Over time, genomic information may become even more revealing than EHR.

5.1.5. Insufficient Personnel

Challenges related to lack of personnel and capacity are mentioned by 13 out of the 25 survey respondents. Workforce limitations are closely linked to funding constraints and represent a significant barrier to the effective management of cohort data. As the data ecosystem continues to evolve, there is a growing demand for professionals with expertise in bioinformatics, data analytics, data engineering, and the handling of sensitive data.

To ensure high-quality data services, there is an urgent need for more data curators and data stewards who can support data holders, especially at the cohort level, by cleaning data, managing quality, and assisting with metadata entry. This highlights the need for a training budget— or for adding content to existing vocational training programmes within EU initiatives. This is particularly important because many cohort studies still rely on manual processes for data capture and metadata annotation, due to a lack of automated or integrated systems. In addition, access to legal expertise to support the processes of data transfer / reuse is often difficult.

This challenge is especially acute at the level of individual cohorts, which often lack the technical and human resources available in larger research infrastructures.

5.1.6. Technology Gaps

Significant technology gaps persist across Europe, particularly in the digital infrastructure, which involve sensitive data and sovereignty of Member States, impacting the support provided to LMedC and biobanks. Technology gaps are reported as a significant challenge by 12 out of the 25 survey respondents. While some institutions are technologically advanced, with centralised, well-managed data lakes and integrated digital services, others continue to operate with minimal infrastructure, in some cases relying on locally stored data on hard drives or siloed, outdated systems. These disparities have serious implications for data quality, accessibility, and scalability.

Although initial project funding or private partnerships may help establish digital platforms, the long-term maintenance and scaling of cloud-based infrastructure remains prohibitively expensive. Without affordable and sustainable solutions for cloud storage, secure computing environments, and data transfer, many biobanks and cohorts are unable to participate fully in EU-wide data-driven initiatives. Additionally, negotiations between LMedC and cloud providers have often been unsatisfactory, particularly when relying on non-European companies. This raises concerns about data sovereignty, governance, and long-term service alignment with EU values.

Europe advancing together technologically on digital services affords a greater linking with international stakeholders - as shown from the interviews the networks with global impact exist but need technology to provide the foundation for their further development.

5.2. Best Practices and Lessons Learnt

In this report, “Best Practices” refers to concrete actions or approaches already being implemented successfully by an organisation or project. The best practices and lessons learnt that the survey participants shared are summarised as follows:

- **Early planning and engagement of all relevant stakeholders**

It is important to create a stakeholder map and initiate focus group discussions as soon as funding is secured. To ensure FAIR data practices, it is essential to bring researchers together early to achieve convergence in data and metadata standards. Involving patient organisations in the project design and maintaining communication throughout its duration can help build trust and ensure alignment with ethical and social standards. To identify any compliance issues with legal or regulatory requirements, ELSI experts should be consulted in the project design phase. One of the main challenges that LMedC face is sustainability. Engaging experts in economics / financing to elaborate tailored business planning can help cohorts secure long-term viability and align with funding opportunities.

- **Strengthen the service offer locally**

National coordination efforts and political will are essential to support harmonisation of cohorts and data practices. Some support and services are most effective when delivered close to researchers. For example, researchers are often more engaged with local service providers than with national or European ones. In addition, universal data harmonisation is challenging due to differing research priorities between high-income and low-income regions. Disease focus areas vary widely, making global standardisation difficult. A more practical approach is to promote regional harmonisation efforts that address local research needs while improving interoperability.

- **Put effort in cohort harmonisation and standardisation**

Successful database development requires early collaboration on protocols. Delaying harmonisation until the analysis stage risks incompatibility across datasets. Avoid retroactive harmonisation by aligning data standards and stakeholder expectations from the start. There is currently no common guidance for researchers establishing new cohorts. Developing shared standards such as core variables and minimum data structures would greatly facilitate interoperability and future data sharing. For example, common fields describing individual participants could improve consistency across studies. An early proof-of-concept for metadata harmonisation is the Maelstrom Research catalogue, which showed how diverse cohort variables can be mapped into a single, machine-readable template. In the end, human data stewards and data curators can never be fully replaced and having such capacity will be needed for good quality metadata. Using clear, standardised consent forms that explicitly allow data sharing and reuse in different contexts is another lesson learnt. Poorly worded or inconsistent forms can block data access and make re-consenting

time-consuming and inefficient. In addition, working with certified and accredited service providers (e.g., ISO standards) that maintain quality management systems should be prioritised. For high-volume services, ensuring the presence of Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS), barcode tracking, and traceability features to support the reliable processing of large sample collections is recommended.

- **Build cohort collaborations**

While organisations often need to differentiate themselves to secure funding, there is greater impact in working toward shared goals. Combining cohort data rather than viewing each cohort in isolation offers stronger research potential. Large national cohorts like UK Biobank already provide comprehensive datasets that can meet many research needs. A key lesson is the importance of continuous communication with cohorts. Not all cohorts are equally prepared or equipped to collaborate. Understanding their goals, needs, and capacities is critical. Some may require targeted training or tools, while others benefit from shared experiences. Instead of assuming a one-size-fits-all approach, creating space for dialogue such as annual meetings and governance discussions helps identify gaps, build trust, and support collaboration. Several organisations provide helpdesks. Having dedicated people answer questions and resolve operational issues has proven to facilitate research.

- **Establish national health data hubs and data catalogues**

Findata collaborations with stakeholder groups have shown that the national dataset catalogue is a very useful research tool. Other entities designing a catalogue, can follow the Findata model: co-design the catalogue with data owners, regulators and researchers so everyone can see via rich metadata what datasets exist and how they can be used. This transparency accelerates discovery and streamlines access requests.

- **Leverage existing cohorts to perform clinical trials**

The Trials within Cohorts (TwiCs) approach uses cohort infrastructures to support the conduct of multiple randomised controlled trials efficiently. The TwiCs design identifies eligible patients from a large observational cohort, randomly selects some for an intervention, and compares their outcomes to those receiving usual care. This approach streamlines recruitment, reduces participant disappointment, and enhances the generalisability of results. Switzerland (CTU Basel) is actively exploring the benefits of the TwiCs approach and raises awareness among researchers, including addressing barriers to its implementation. In these cases, having an informed consent process mentioning that participants may be randomised into a trial saves much time from having to re-contact and re-consent participants.

- **Transparency builds trust**

UK Biobank has a policy requiring researchers to return any data generated using its datasets. This expectation, embedded into the terms and conditions of access and material transfer agreements, promotes transparency and enables further data reuse by the research

community. The IHCC pairs discovery-driven cohorts with clinical implementation sites. In Singapore, a centrally funded cohort of 100.000 participants (aiming for one million) has already converted several genomic findings into actionable tools for patient care. IHCC is now helping transfer these insights to neighboring Malaysia so local physicians can apply the same evidence in a population with shared ancestry, illustrating how cross-border knowledge exchange turns cohort discoveries into clinical impact. To cite the interviewee from Findata, *“No trust equals no data”*.

5.3. Recommendations for Strengthening Infrastructure Support

Based on this mapping exercise and the input received via the survey and the follow-up interviews, WP4 makes the following recommendations to policy- and decision-makers:

- **Ensure sustainable, long-term funding for LMedC**

Policymakers should establish dedicated, long-term funding mechanisms tailored to the specific needs of cohort and longitudinal studies. This includes multi-year, renewable funding frameworks that ensure financial stability for essential research infrastructure such as biobanking, data curation, and long-term archiving. Such mechanisms should move beyond short-term, project-based grants and enable sustained strategic planning, capacity building, and retention of expertise. Greater alignment between funding instruments and the inherently long-term nature of these studies is essential to safeguard their continuity, maximize their scientific value, and foster resilience in the research ecosystem. The cohorts funding scheme could follow a model similar to the one of ESFRIs.

- **Promote regulatory harmonisation and legal clarity for cohort research in the EU**

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has not fully addressed data sharing challenges in cohort research, with the derogations available with respect to research leading to different interpretations and national legislation variations across the European Economic Area (EEA). The evolving legal landscape, including Data Governance Act, Data Act, AI Act, and EHDS regulation, emphasises the need for clear guidance, policies, and best practices for health researchers, especially those preparing data for long-term storage or sharing. Most of the cohort studies (except for pharmacoepidemiology cohorts) do not fall under the EU Clinical Trials Regulation (Regulation EU No 536/2014), which is partly the reason behind the high heterogeneity in the design and conduct of cohort studies.

- **Promote the use of data standards to improve interoperability**

In the rapidly evolving health-related data ecosystem, a vast array of data types emerges from diverse sources, encompassing clinical observations, biomarker tests, genetics, radiology images, surveys, and more, collected across various contexts such as routine healthcare, clinical research, and population studies. These data can pose significant challenges, including varying languages, unstructured textual components, and diverse units for numeric components. Even data of a similar type can exhibit different structures

and employ distinct vocabulary and ontology systems. Exploring how to accelerate adoption of relevant data standards by LMedC (e.g., CDISC, OMOP, DICOM, GA4GH) would improve interoperability and facilitate secondary use. A trade-off needs to be found between standardisation, and freedom for innovation in the selection of variables.

- **Improve cohort findability and access**

There is a need to establish an EU-based central cohort registry and to promote cohort metadata standards. The system could build upon the CTIS registry for clinical trials. As cohort registration is not mandatory, it is impossible to determine which cohorts are active and where they are being conducted. Improving findability is thus a prerequisite for scalability, at the national, European and global levels. The implementation of the EHDS regulation is expected to bring some harmonisation for discovery metadata (e.g., via the use of Health-DCAT-AP) and access processes (via Health Data Access Bodies-HDABs).

- **Build privacy-preserving infrastructures and tools**

Support the development of privacy-preserving technologies and infrastructures such as distributed computing models and Trusted Research Environments (TREs) or Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) to enable secure, ethical, and legally compliant (e.g., compliant with the future EHDS specifications) cohort research. These models allow sensitive data to remain within local jurisdictions while enabling collaborative analysis, thereby minimizing risks related to data sharing and re-identification. A commonly accepted definition and tools for “anonymisation” and approved methodologies for synthetic data validation would also result in a wider use of LMedC.

- **Create EU-based GDPR-compliant cloud storage and archiving capacity for health research data**

Policymakers should urgently invest in the development of a sovereign, EU-wide digital infrastructure capable of supporting the long-term cloud storage, archiving, and processing needs of cohort and health research data. This includes creating publicly governed, interoperable cloud platforms aligned with [GAIA-X](#) principles and integrated into the EHDS. These platforms must provide secure, affordable, and scalable environments for storing and analysing sensitive datasets, such as high-resolution imaging and multi-omics files, that are rapidly growing to petabyte and exabyte scales. The [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#) initiative should provide expertise and technical infrastructure towards this direction.

- **Invest in training and capacity building**

Targeted funding and training programs are needed to expand the pool of experts in bioinformatics, data stewardship, legal compliance, and metadata curation. Special attention should be given to supporting individual cohort studies, which often operate with limited resources and staff. Policies should encourage the creation of dedicated roles such as data curators, stewards, and legal advisors and promote the adoption of automated systems to reduce reliance on manual processes.

- **Coordinate between existing Research Infrastructures and service providers**

As indicated through our mapping exercise, the current service provision landscape has the expertise needed to support LMedC. What is missing is improving visibility, scaling-up and coordination across the different cohort owners and service providers. Sometimes repurposing existing services (e.g., anonymisation or federated analysis tools developed in other disciplines) can be useful to cover the needs of the LMedC community. It is crucial to leverage existing infrastructure and better adopt it to fit user needs, while keeping in mind that global cooperation is needed for efficient cohort studies. Our recommendation is to create a “single access body” grouping all the service offer for LMedC and coordinating across service providers.

6. CONCLUSION

This mapping exercise reveals a rich but fragmented landscape of infrastructure services supporting LMedC across Europe. There are several service providers with expertise in *Data Services*, *Regulatory and Ethical Support (ELSI)*, *Methodology and Design*, *Biobanking and OMICs* and *Operational Support and Coordination*. Despite this fact, most service providers do not offer a full-spectrum service coverage. In addition, many service providers operate at national (e.g., Health-RI, NFDI4Health, France Cohortes) or even regional level (e.g., UMCG) demonstrating a strong need to build synergies, harmonise practices and legal requirements within the EEA to allow these infrastructures to scale up and adapt their services for pan-European users. Data and metadata harmonisation and use of standards would greatly improve cohort findability and reusability. In many countries, and in view of the upcoming EHDS ecosystem, aspects like data quality, metadata and data standardisation are being tackled, although some uncertainties around their final implementation remain. The next steps within INTEGRATE-LMedC WP4 involve the collection of user needs (T4.2) and the conduct of a gap analysis comparing user expectations against the current infrastructure service provision landscape (T4.3).

Deliverable 4.1 lays the groundwork for moving forward with confidence; however, a couple of limitations need to be acknowledged:

- i) The mapping exercise offers only a partial reflection of the European service landscape for large medical cohorts (LMedC). While 25 organisations of varying profiles were selected and included, the report does not claim to provide a comprehensive overview, which would be unfeasible within the available time and resources.
- ii) Survey respondents and interviewees represented the identified service providers; however, their perspectives may be influenced by their specific roles and responsibilities within their organisations. As such, their knowledge of the full-service portfolio or reporting on organisational activities may include some biases.
- iii) The analysis presents a snapshot of the situation until spring 2025. As several service providers indicated they are actively expanding or adapting their service offerings, some information presented in this report may become outdated over time.

Acknowledgements

We extend our sincere thanks to all participating organisations for sharing their valuable expertise, insights, and lessons learnt. Their contributions have been instrumental in shaping this mapping and charting a clearer path forward for strengthening support to large medical cohorts across Europe.

ANNEXES

Annex 1: REDCap Survey, Mapping Infrastructure Services and Tools for Large Medical

Cohorts

Annex 2: Specialisation Index (SI) – Calculation Methodology and Example

Annex 3: Summary of Partner-Reported Services, Tools, and Capacities Based on Interviews Conducted

ANNEX 1

REDCap Survey: Page 1 of 7.

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Page 1

Mapping Infrastructure Services and Tools for Large Medical Cohorts

Estimated time to complete: 10-15 minutes

This questionnaire is part of the EU-funded INTEGRATE-LMedC project, where LMedC stands for Large Medical Cohorts. The INTEGRATE-LMedC initiative aims to guide and support decision making for the development of a comprehensive portfolio of infrastructure services, facilitating the efficient utilisation and harmonization of large medical cohorts (LMCs).

As part of Work Package 4, this questionnaire maps the current European Research Infrastructure landscape, identifying available services, capacities and tools at national, European and international levels to support large medical cohorts. The collected data will highlight existing services and areas for improvement.

The questionnaire will be distributed via email, followed by targeted follow-up interviews with key organisations and Research Infrastructures or Projects and Initiatives that provide services and tools to support design, planning, conduct and exploitation of large medical cohorts. These insights will contribute to a comprehensive mapping of user needs, which will be compared against existing services in a gap analysis to identify areas requiring further development.

Your input is essential in shaping the future of research infrastructure for large medical cohorts.

For simplicity, the term 'organisation(s)' will collectively refer to Organisations, Research Infrastructures, Projects, and Initiatives throughout this questionnaire.

Thank you for your time and contribution.

CONSENT TO PROCESS PERSONAL DATA

Do you consent to the processing of your personal data and the sharing of the information you provide for the questionnaire? (Please find the data protection policy regarding the processing of personal data and the sharing of information provided through this questionnaire.)

WP4-Consent Form-QuestionnaireLMedC.pdf

To proceed with the questionnaire, you must select 'Yes'. If you select 'No', the questionnaire will automatically close.

Yes No

Thank you for your time.

Since your consent is required to proceed, we regret that the questionnaire cannot continue. If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact us (sara.raza-khan@ecrn.org).

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Section 2: Services, Tools and Capacities

7. Which of the following services does your organisation or project provide to support large medical cohorts? (Select all that apply)

- Design
- Methodology and Statistical Planning
- Protocol Review
- Cohort Protocol Registration
- Planning (advice, research support, consultation, etc.)
- Conduct
- Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues (ELSI) Support
- Data Services
- Patient Recruitment
- Patient Engagement
- Biobanking and Sample Management
- OMICS Analyses (e.g., environmental, imaging, lifestyle, and other data)
- Training and Capacity Building
- Dissemination
- Other services (please specify)

If you chose Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI) Support, please specify (Select all that apply)

- Ethics and Informed Consent
- Legal and Regulatory Advice
- Data Protection Advice
- Regulatory, Ethical Approvals, and Amendments

If you chose Data Services, please specify (Select all that apply)

- Data Management Plan (DMP)
- Case Report Form(CRF) Development
- Data Management Services
- Data Monitoring/Quality Control
- Data Harmonization and Standards
- Data Integration
- Secondary Use of Electronic Health Records (EHR)
- Cohort Data Secondary Use
- Cohort Data Sharing
- Biostatistics and Data Analysis
- Other Services

If your organisation provides additional services, not listed above, please specify (Open Text Field)

8. What tools and capacities enable your organisation to provide services to large medical cohorts (Short Text Field)

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Section 3: Access, Eligibility, Cost and Geographic Scope

9. Would you consider your organisation to be service-oriented and accessible to external users?

- Yes
 No
-

10. Does your organisation focus on: (Select all that apply)

- Prospective Cohort Development
 Retrospective Use of Cohort Data
-

11. Does your organisation focus on specific diseases?

- Yes No
-

If yes, please specify diseases (e.g., cancer, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, etc.) (Open Text Field)

12. Does your organisation focus on a specific population (e.g., age, socio-economic status, occupational cohorts, etc.)?

- Yes No
-

If yes, please specify population group(s) (Open Text Field)

13. Does your organisation (or project) have eligibility criteria or access procedures for providing services to large medical cohorts?

- Yes
 No
 Other
-

If you selected 'Other', please briefly describe the eligibility criteria or access procedures (Open Text Field)

14. What is the access model for providing services? (Select all that apply)

- Virtual Access
 Consulting
 Operational Services
 Other Access Models
-

If your organisation uses other access models for providing services, please specify (Short Text Field)

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15. What is the cost model for your organisation to provide these services? (Select all that apply)

- Cost of services covered by sustainable, core funding of service provider
- Cost of services covered through research project(s)
- Cost of services covered by fees for services
- Other

Other cost models, if applicable, please specify (Open Text Field)

16. What is the reach of your organisation for service provision? (Select all that apply)

- National
- Regional
- European
- International or Extra European
- Any Other Comments

If you chose 'Any Other Comments', please specify (Open Text Field)

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Section 4: Challenges and Best Practices

17. What are the main challenges your organisation (or project) faces when providing services to large medical cohorts? (Select all that apply)

- Changing Regulatory Ecosystem
- Evolving Data Ecosystem
- Technology Gaps
- Insufficient Personnel
- Funding Limitations
- Privacy, Security and Ethical Concerns
- Other Challenges

If your organisation faces additional challenges, not listed here, please specify (Open Text Field)

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Section 5: Collaborations and Recommendations

18. Does your organisation collaborate with other entities to support large medical cohorts?

Yes No

If yes, please list key collaborators (Open Text Field)

19. Would you like to recommend any additional organisations that we should contact for mapping infrastructure services and tools for large medical cohorts? (Short Text Field)

Thank you for completing the questionnaire.

We will follow up via email to schedule a 30-40 minute interview for additional insights. During the interview, we would appreciate your input on the following points:

Are there any best practices or lessons learned that you would like to share? What additional tools or services would you recommend to better support large medical cohorts? What recommendations do you have for improving service provision to large medical cohorts at the European or global level?

ANNEX 2

Specialisation Index (SI) – Calculation Methodology

The **Specialisation Index (SI)** was used to assess how focused each provider is within a defined set of five service clusters. It reflects the proportion of a provider's contribution to each cluster, normalised across their entire profile. This allowed for a clearer understanding of the distribution of services and areas of focus for each provider, regardless of their overall size or total number of services offered.

Service Clusters Included in the Mapping

This mapping includes five clusters of services, with the total number of services included in the survey within each cluster shown in the parentheses:

Cluster 1: Data Services (11 services)

Cluster 2: Regulatory and Ethical Services (ELSI) (4 services)

Cluster 3: Methodology and Design (5 services)

Cluster 4: Biobanking and OMICS Analysis (2 services)

Cluster 5: Operational Support and Coordination (5 services)

Step-by-Step Calculation

1. Counting Services Offered by a Service Provider in Each Cluster

For each provider, the number of services offered in each service cluster was counted.

a = Number of services offered by the provider in each cluster

b = Total number of services offered in that cluster (as per survey questions)

2. Calculating the Provider's Share of Each Cluster

The number of services offered by the provider in a cluster (**a**) was divided by the total number of services in that cluster (**b**) to compute their share:

$$c = \frac{a}{b}$$

This value (**c**) represents how much the provider contributes to the given service cluster.

3. Repeating the Calculation for All Clusters

This calculation was repeated for each provider across all five clusters. The resulting five values of **c** were summed for each provider:

$$d = \sum c$$

This total (**d**) represented the provider's total contributions across all clusters.

4. Normalising to Calculate the Specialisation Index (SI)

Each cluster value (**c**) was then divided by the provider's total across all clusters (**d**) to calculate the **Specialisation Index**:

$$SI = \frac{c}{d}$$

The five SI values for each provider always sum to 1. This makes it possible to see the **distribution of focus** across the five clusters for any given provider.

Interpretation of Results in the SI Table:

- The SI values for each provider across the 5 clusters always sums to 1.
- The maximum possible SI is 1, indicating that the service provider contributes to only one cluster.
- The minimum meaningful SI value is 0.2, which reflects an even distribution of services across all five clusters.
- An SI close to 1 indicates that the provider is highly specialised in that particular cluster.
- An SI near 0.2 suggests that services are evenly distributed across the clusters.
- An SI below 0.2 reflects a lower focus in that cluster relative to the others.
- An SI of 0 means the provider offers no services in that cluster.

This approach highlights the distribution of activity within each provider's service portfolio, without ranking or comparing providers against one another.

An illustrative example based on data from Table 4 is provided below.

Example:

Services Offered by ECRIN to LMedC

Clusters	a (ECRIN Services)	b (Total Services in Cluster)	C=a/b
Data Services	7	11	0.64
Regulatory and Ethical Services (ELSI)	2	4	0.5
Methodology and Design	5	5	1
Biobanking and OMICS	0	2	0
Operational Support and Coordination	3	5	0.6
Sum of c Values Across Clusters ($\sum c=d$)			2.74

This yielded the proportion of the total cluster services (d) that were contributed by ECRIN.

Specialisation Index (SI) for ECRIN Services

Example ECRIN	SI= c/d	SI values	Rounded values
Data Services	=0.64 / 2.74	0.23	0.2
Regulatory and Ethical Services (ELSI)	= 0.5 / 2.74	0.18	0.2
Methodology and Design	= 1 / 2.74	0.37	0.4
Biobanking and OMICS	0	0	0
Operational Support and Coordination	= 0.6 / 2.74	0.22	0.2
Total SI		1.00	1.00

This index shows that while ECRIN specialises in Methodology and Design (SI = 0.37), Data Services (SI = 0.23), and Operational Support and Coordination (SI = 0.22), there is a lesser focus on Regulatory and Ethical Services (SI = 0.18), and no contribution to Biobanking and OMICS Analysis (SI = 0.00).

Note: For ease of readability, SI values in Table 4 have been rounded, and zero values are displayed as blank cells.

ANNEX 3

Summary of Partner-Reported Services, Tools, and Capacities Based on Interviews Conducted

1.	BBMRI-ERIC	Provides a well-established suite of tools: the Directory, a catalogue for biobank discovery, the Negotiator, for access request management, and the Federated Platform tools (Locator and Finder) which are more specialized. The Locator provides access to the samples and associated data based on real-time search on donor and sample level, whereas the <i>Finder</i> is a data analysis tool focused on clinical, phenotypic and genomics data. BBMRI-ERIC supports researchers with ELSI (Ethical, Legal and Social Issues) training and dedicated resources.
2.	BIN	The BioImaging Portugal Node (BIN) is the national imaging infrastructure of Portugal and a member of Euro-BioImaging ERIC . BIN provides advanced imaging technologies and data services for biomedical research, including support for phenotyping, image-based biomarkers, and longitudinal studies. Through its facilities, BIN offers access to FAIR-compliant data management tools and cutting-edge imaging platforms relevant to large medical cohorts.
3.	CNAG	CNAG provides extensive sequencing capabilities, including genome/exome/RNA sequencing, medium scale single cell/ spatial transcriptome sequencing and analysis. It hosts the RD-Connect Genome-Phenome Analysis Platform (GPAP) , a secure, GDPR compliant platform that allows management, analysis and integration of genomic and phenotypic data and allows federated, large scale whole genome/ exome/ exome/ RNA sequencing and analysis. GPAP is a rich resource of sequencing data from pseudonymised rare disease patients and family members. It facilitates collation, discovery, sharing, analysis and interpretation of standardised genome-phenome data within a controlled collaborative environment. The platform facilitates collaborative projects by enabling authorised users to tag variants, and link clinical and genomic data for thousands of rare disease patients and relatives, contributing to research on diagnosis and gene. After an optional embargo period, the data are shared with other platform users, to maximise the chances to eventually diagnose the cases.
4.	Clinical Trial Unit (Basel)	Clinical Trial Unit (CTU) Basel contributes specialised expertise in clinical research methodology and trial planning, particularly in Trials within Cohorts (TwiCS). It offers consulting for clinical and cohort linked studies involving investigational products, devices, study registries, clinical studies for cohort projects or research with routine data.
5.	EBRAINS	EBRAINS coordinates a pan-European network of neuroscience services. Key services include 3D brain atlases, computational models, and platforms for validating and inferring models against diverse datasets. EBRAINS also fosters collaboration (via Collab tools) among researchers by providing access to metadata frameworks for brain data, data curation services, metadata management (Knowledge Graph), access to data storage for anonymous data/metadata, services for requesting access to controlled/restricted data storages for pseudonymized data. Training and education is also delivered to researchers across career stages.
6.	European Clinical	ECRIN is a distributed research infrastructure, it provides services for

	Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN)	cohort studies: design & planning, where applicable regulatory and ethical support, monitoring (if applicable), project management/overall coordination. ECRIN also offers tools such as clinical research data sharing repository (crDSR), clinical research metadata repository (crMDR). ECRIN maintains RED (Regulatory and ethical Database) that includes guidance for non-interventional or observational studies.
7.	EIRENE	EIRENE aims to create new capacities for human exposome research and assessment of risks associated with environmental exposures by developing a network of harmonized laboratories, environmental studies, population cohorts (e.g., birth cohorts), and databases. The focus of EIRENE is not on medical cohorts. EIRENE has strong statistical and bioinformatics capacities and ELSI expertise. In addition, they possess biobanks and high-capacity OMICs laboratories (genomics, proteomics, metabolomics) for the analysis of anthropogenic chemicals (organic / inorganic / metals) in environmental samples, food, feed, water and human matrices. Toxicology studies and small-animal models are also employed to examine adverse effects.
8.	ELIXIR	ELIXIR supports data-intensive life science research and promotes standards for data sharing, interoperability, and compute resources. It links up communities of experts in data management across >20 countries. It offers a range of compute capabilities, bio.tools registry of software metadata and descriptions, data management, web portals for softwares, training courses and standards and opportunities for collaboration and funding.
9.	Estonian Biobank	Estonian Biobank offers end-to-end support for cohort studies including design, logistics, IT development, sequencing, data integration with national registries. With a population-based cohort size of more than 200,000 individuals (genotyped with genome-wide arrays), reflecting the age, sex and geographical distribution of the adult Estonian population, the biobank offers harmonised data pipelines and infrastructure for genomic and phenotypic research.
10.	Euro-Biolmaging (EuBI)	EuBI and its European nodes support large medical cohorts through advanced imaging technologies such as MRI, PET, CT, alongside expert consulting on study design, methodology, and data analysis. The infrastructure provides secure data management, high-performance computing, and AI-powered image analysis for handling large datasets. Training, standardised protocols, and ELSI support are also offered to ensure data privacy, compliance and high-quality large-scale imaging studies. The EuBI Node, Biobank Innovation Centre, BIN delivers advanced imaging services including MRI and PET, biosample logistics, medical and study nursing support, and a data science unit with AI capabilities along with a clinical trial unit. Even though affiliated with EuBI, in this mapping exercise, BIN has been counted as a separate organisation.
11.	Findata	Findata offers a National Data Resources Catalogue , a metadata catalogue. It also provides secure data processing environment, Kapseli , for the processing of data on individuals where researchers can use the primary statistical software for analysing the data, and case management tools for controlled access to Finnish health data. Anyone can apply for data, national register-based studies are possible in Finland.
12.	France Cohortes	France Cohorts supports scientists in their cohort projects, promoting

		<p>public health research. It offers a powerful, secure hosting solution, within the repository of the national health data system (Système National des Données de Santé, SNDS), ensuring GDPR compliance in a systematic, centralized manner. It offers a comprehensive integrated platform supporting data collection, analysis (including ML), FAIR data stewardship, and regulatory compliance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Information System: Support for data collection, computerized questionnaires development and administration, integration of clinical and medical devices data, to data structuring, cleaning, and statistical analysis. ○ Open Science and FAIR Principles: Guidance for adopting FAIR and open science practices, including the development of standardised documentation. ○ Protocol Design: Guidance in designing data collection protocols, questionnaire content and standards, communication strategies and participant engagement methods. ○ Data Management: Assistance in implementing robust and reproducible data management systems with features such as applying repositories, record linkage, deduplication, pseudonymization, and the use of data compatible with algorithmic sharing. ○ Cohort Collaboration and Integration: Facilitate collaboration with digital health stakeholders such as the Health Data Hub, the National Health Agency (Agence National de la Santé, ANS), and the National Health Insurance Fund (Caisse Nationale de l'Assurance Maladie, CNAM), including shared tools and infrastructure.
13.	Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering (IBMT)	<p>The fields of expertise of the Fraunhofer IBMT include biomedical/medical engineering, medical (molecular and cellular) biotechnology, biohybrid technology, bioprocessing and bioanalytics, cryo(bio)technology and nano(bio)technology, ultrasound technology, biomedical microsystems, neuroprosthetics and implants, health information systems, theranostics, (mobile) laboratory technology as well as laboratory automation including in-line/on-line process control. For more than 10 years, Fraunhofer IBMT has been working in the field of stem cell research and hosting extensive cell line stocks in industrial and clinically structured biobanks for low temperature storage of valuable samples (fluids, cells, tissue fragments).</p>
14.	Fundació Sant Joan de Déu (FSJD)	<p>It provides a broad range of services to support large medical cohorts, particularly in the design and planning of studies and in data services. Their expertise includes support for data analysis, data management, and facilitating the secondary use of health data, in line with ethical and legal requirements. FSJD also coordinated the SYNCHROS project, a European initiative aimed at advancing the coordination and integration of large population cohorts, which was included in this mapping exercise through a dedicated interview.</p>
15.	Health-RI	<p>Health-RI operates the National Health Data Portal and a Data Catalogue that collects, organizes and gives access to health_ related data at national level, or to collaborative international projects if there is a collaboration with the Netherlands. Health-RI is operating an ELSI Servicedesk available at https://elsi.health-ri.nl/.</p>
16.	International Agency for Research on Cancer World Health Organisation IARC/WHO	<p>The IARC/WHO is a specialized agency of the World Health Organization with extensive experience in supporting large medical cohorts globally. IARC leads and collaborates on international cohort studies such as EPIC, providing expertise in study design, epidemiology, data harmonisation, and ethical governance. The agency also contributes to capacity building and infrastructure development in low- and middle-income countries,</p>

		making it a key global actor in longitudinal research.
17.	International Health Cohorts Consortium (IHCC)	IHCC is a global community that links 89 cohorts across 42 countries. The initiative supports planning, conducting, maintaining and analyzing large medical cohorts. The consortium is open to all, with an agreement that researchers will share data if they join. Its Cohort Atlas Browser enables standardisation and discoverability of cohort data.
18.	Maelstrom Research	Maelstrom Research's activities are founded on the data harmonization methodology developed under the DataSHaPER ¹ project, the open-source software developed by the OBiBa team ² , and the federated data analysis methodology developed under the DataSHIELD ³ project. It offers open-source tools for cohort data harmonisation and management (e.g., madshapR and Rmonize, OBiBa software suite) and facilitates data discoverability with its metadata Maelstrom Catalogue . It participates in international collaborations that foster and enhance the use of epidemiological study data.
19.	NFDI4Health	NFDI4Health is the German national research data infrastructure for personal health data in Germany. It aims to make health data FAIR through metadata generation, and centralized study registration for all researchers working in domains of clinical trials, epidemiological studies and public health studies. It offers tools for federated data analyses and the possibility of study registration on the German Central Health Study Hub . It is developing a dedicated ELSI helpdesk as part of its next phase.
20.	ORCHESTRA -Connecting European Cohorts to Increase Common and Effective Response to SARS-CoV-2 Pandemic	ORCHESTRA, an international pandemic-focused research project, now ended, led by the University of Verona, united 26 partners from 15 countries to integrate over 20 population and clinical cohorts, including from EU and LMIC settings. It established a federated, interoperable cohort model to support pandemic preparedness and response. Through standardised protocols, harmonised data tools, and GDPR-aligned governance frameworks, ORCHESTRA enabled cross-border data pooling and ethical reuse—offering a scalable model for future international cohort research. It has ended now.
21.	Research Data Alliance (RDA)	Research Data Alliance (RDA), launched in 2013 by the EC, NSF and Australian Government's Department of innovation facilitates global collaboration on data sharing through 60 Interest Groups and 38 Working groups (listed on RDA Website , 12,600 members from 145 countries). Individual membership to the RDA is free for anyone that supports the RDA mission and its guiding principles. The Sensitive Data Interest Group offers best practices and policy recommendations for managing sensitive health data and have developed some tools, such as Metadata Standards Directory , Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data .
22.	Sciensano	Sciensano provides support in data governance and metadata management and capacity building technical guidance and training workshops.
23.	SYNCHROS project	The SYNCHROS project, although now ended, has developed practical ELSI guidelines and global best practices to improve international cohort coordination ⁴ . It has contributed to cohort harmonisation through coordinated, foundation-led research and international stakeholder engagement.
24.	University Medical	UMCG hosts the Cohort and Biobank Coordination Hub (CBCH) , a central

	Center Groningen (UMCG)	<p>structure offering tools and services to strengthen development and sustainability of UMCG-led cohorts and collaborations in the Netherlands. Services offered include standard templates (protocol, informed consent, budget templates, etc.), advisory services: Service desk for questions. A Research Data Catalogue allows users to browse 128 data and sample of clinical studies, cohorts, databanks and biobanks for reuse and collaboration. Initially called 'molecular genetics information system', MOLGENIS platform, has evolved into a broader tool to include biobanking, rare disease research, patient registries, and data catalogues. It provides software infrastructures to capture, exchange, and exploit the large amounts of data being produced by scientific organisations all around the world. UMCG offers advice, storage and management of biomaterials for its own cohorts and for external institutes and companies through its Central Freezer Storage Facility. This Dutch academic center aims makes health data accessible to researchers, policy makers, citizens, health care providers and the business community, and enables users to find and obtain data, tools and training.</p>
25.	UK Biobank	<p>UK Biobank is a large-scale biomedical database and research resource containing securely accessible de-identified genetic, lifestyle and health information and biological samples from half a million UK participants. All data is now available (with limited exceptions) on UK Biobank's cloud-based Research Analysis Platform (UKB-RAP). Its goal is to make data available world-wide to researchers on modest charges, financial credits and grants are also offered for LMIC. It is the most comprehensive and widely used dataset of its kind and is globally accessible to approved researchers who are undertaking health-related research that is in the public interest, whether the rare from academic, commercial, government or charitable settings. UK Biobank is a longitudinal study; it follows the health of 500,000 volunteer participants.</p>